

OPTIMAL PLACEMENT OF DISTRIBUTED GENERATION IN RADIAL DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM USING DRAGONFLY ALGORITHM

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Abstract: This paper presents a method for optimal placement of Distributed Generation (DG) in radial distribution system using Dragonfly Algorithm (DA). Minimization of active power losses of distribution system has been considered as an objective function. Voltage limits and thermal limit of feeders in radial distribution system have been considered as constraints of optimization problem. The proposed method has been implemented on PG & E 69 bus and IEEE 15 bus radial distribution system. Reduction of active power losses of radial distribution system by choosing proper location and size of DG units using proposed method has been observed in simulation results.

Index Terms - Distributed Generation (DG), Dragonfly Algorithm (DA), Active power losses, Radial distribution system (RDS), Optimal placement.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, the penetration of embedded generator resources in distribution network has been increased globally. New local government policies towards reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and mitigation of global warming is the main reason for such penetration. Loss reduction, on peak operating cost reduction, improvement in network reinforcement horizon, service quality, reliability, power quality and voltage support [1], [2] are the benefits seen by the penetration of EG units into the distribution system. Traditional distribution systems are passive in nature. These passive distribution systems are transformed into active distribution system like transmission system upon integration of DG units [3]. There are many technical issues like increasing steady state voltage at minimum voltage bus and reduction of active power losses have been considered for connecting the DG units in to the radial distribution system [4].

Many approaches have been existing in literature for determining the optimal location and size of DG units in radial distribution system. Conventional optimization techniques, metaheuristic techniques and artificial intelligence are normally used to solve this type of optimal placement problem [5]. Conventional techniques usually suffer from the problem of convergence at local minimum instead of at global. Hence these methods are not suggestible for solving problems which have a large number of local minimum points. Whereas heuristic and evolutionary algorithms are powerful and effective for solving complex real time problems [6].

Ant Colony Search Algorithm (ACSA) was used for solving the optimal allocation problem in [7]. This algorithm is inspired from the natural behaviour of the ant colonies on how they find the food source and bring them back to their nest by building the unique trail formation. However, the rates of ant colony regulating parameters need to be determined using experimental approach [8].

Evolutionary Programming (EP) was used to solve the optimal placement of DG units in radial distribution system in [9]. In this method sensitive indices which are developed from voltage stability index have been used for selecting the optimal location of DG units. Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm was used for identifying the optimal location and size of DG units in radial distribution system based on active power losses in [10]. Genetic Algorithm was used for optimal placement of DG based on active power losses and voltage rise in [11] and based on active power losses in [5]. However genetic algorithm has some flaws like problem in finding the exact solution and slow convergence [12].

In this paper first time Dragonfly Algorithm (DA) has been used for solving the optimization problem i.e. optimal allocation of DG units in radial distribution system. Minimization of active power losses of distribution system has been considered as an objective function. Location in terms of bus number in distribution system and size of DG in terms of generating capacity are considered as decision variables. Voltage limits at each bus and thermal limit of each line in distribution system have been considered as constraints in this optimization problem.

The remaining part of the paper has been organized as:

Section II describes about problem formulation, section III presents simulation results of the proposed method and section IV presents conclusions of this paper.